

Comparison of Three Methods for Quadratic Potential Propagators Part II

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In a previous note (Part I), we compared three methods for computing the propagator for a quadratic potential: $b(t)x^2 + m f(t)x dx/dt$. The first method (1) is based on assuming the form $Q(t) \exp\{-i [b(t)XX + e(t)YY + g(t)XY] \}$ which is inserted into the time-dependent Schrodinger equation and coefficients of XX equated to obtain a differential equation. Other differential equations for $Q(t)$, $e(t)$ and $g(t)$ may be found in a similar manner. The second approach (2) is to compute a Green's function by first converting $m f(t)x dx/dt$ into $d/dt [.5 m f(t) x^2] - .5 m df/dt x^2$ and then throw away the $d/dt []$ term because it does not affect the equations of motion. The third approach is to calculate $Q(t) \exp(-i \text{Action})$ where $\text{Action} = \int dt L$ where L is the classical Lagrangian. We showed that $b(t)$ may be linked to the $A(t)$, a solution of the classical equations of motion.

In this note, we first argue that $d/dt [.5 m f(t) x^2]$ should be retained in the Lagrangian as it contributes to $Q(t) \exp(i \text{Action})$ whether or not it affects the equations of motion. Second, we show that not only are $b(t)$ and $A(t)$ linked, but this link has the form $\exp(-i \text{Action})$ for constant mass and a potential of the form $g(t)x^2$. In other words, one may start with the time-dependent Schrodinger equation and establish a propagator $Q(t) \exp\{-i [b(t)XX + e(t)YY + g(t)XY] \}$ with no link whatsoever to classical physics (other than the form of H the Hamiltonian). The factor $b(t)$ may be directly linked to the classical equation of motion (as shown in part I) and from this one may demonstrate that the propagator is in fact $\exp(-i \text{Action})$. In this note, we only consider the XX term and m constant. For a constant mass and a potential of the form $g_1(t)x^2 + m f(t)x dx/dt$, there is no match. In the case of a time-dependent mass, we also find that the Schrodinger equation approach (1) no longer matches $\exp(i \text{Action})$.

Converting $m f(t)x dx/dt$ Into $d/dt [.5 m f(t) x^2] - .5 m df/dt x^2$

In (2), the potential term $m f(t)x dx/dt$ is converted into $d/dt [.5 m f(t) x^2] - .5 m df/dt x^2$ and the term $d/dt [.5 m f(t) x^2]$ eliminated from the Lagrangian as it does not affect the equations of motion. Thus, $m f(t)x dx/dt$ becomes part of a $g(t)x^2$ potential. For the $\exp(-i \text{Action})$ approach of the computation the propagator, the term $d/dt []$ is simply evaluated in the action: $\int dt d/dt [.5 m f(t) x^2] = [.5 m f(t) x^2]$ at the endpoints, thus we suggest it should be retained.

Given that the term $m f(t)x dx/dt$ is changed in the Lagrangian, one may try to change it in the potential of the Schrodinger equation, but this leads to a problem because x and t are independent variables in the quantum case. This shows that there may even be an issue for $\exp(-i \text{Action})$ because the action may be converted using $L = L(k_1(t)x^2) + d/dt [.5 m f(t) x^2]$. From the point of view of classical equations of motion, $d/dt [.5 m f(t) x^2]$ may be thrown away, but if retained in $\exp(-i \text{Action})$ yielding $\exp(-i XX .5 m f(t))$, this piece does not cancel from the time-dependent Schrodinger equation. Imagine one has $b = b_0 + .5 m f$, then the Schrodinger equation pieces

associated with f are $[\exp(-i(b_{osc} + .5mf)XX)]$ inserted into $i\frac{d}{dt}P = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dX} \frac{d}{dX} P + k(t) + f(t)x$ $(-i\frac{d}{dx})P$

$$\text{LHS } .5m\frac{df}{dt} \quad \text{RHS } \frac{4}{2m} (.5mf)(.5mf) + \frac{4}{2m} (2) b_{osc} .5mf + 2(b_{osc} + .5mf) f - .5 \frac{df}{dt} + Z \quad ((1a))$$

The regular oscillator pieces are: $\frac{d b_{osc}}{dt} = \frac{4}{2m} b_{osc} b_{osc} + k(t)$ ((1b)) which may be satisfied by $b_{osc} = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{dA}{dt} / A$ as will be shown later where $k(t)$ is replaced using the classical equation of motion: $k(t) = -m/2 \frac{d}{dt} \frac{dA}{dt} + f/2 A$ with $Z = f/2 A$. ((1a)) is not satisfied under these circumstances unless $f(t)$ is restricted to the solution of a certain differential equation. From ((1a)), one may see that coefficients of ff do not cancel.

Thus, even though classical physics allows one to use either L or $L_1 = L + \frac{d}{dt} [.5mf xx]$ to obtain the same equations of motion, the two corresponding Schrodinger equations have different propagators and different potentials. In one case, $\exp(-i \text{Action})$ matches the propagator obtained by inserting $\exp(-i b(t) XX + \dots)$ into the Schrodinger equation, and in the second case it doesn't. In particular, a quadratic potential of the form $k(t)xx$ leads to a match. We investigate this in the following sections.

Computation of the Classical Action

Consider first the simpler problem of:

$$L = m/2 \frac{dx}{dt} \frac{dx}{dt} - b(t)xx \quad ((1c))$$

To calculate the Lagrangian, one first uses:

$$x(t) = XA(T_f - t)/A(T) + YA(t - 0)/A(T) \quad ((2)) \text{ as in (3).}$$

Here we are only interested in XX coefficients. Thus:

$$\text{Action (XX part)} = \frac{1}{[A(T)A(T)]} \int dt \frac{m}{2} \frac{dA}{dt} \frac{dA}{dt} - k(t) AA \quad ((4))$$

The equation of motion is: $m \frac{d}{dt} \frac{dA}{dt} + 2k(t)A = 0$ ((5)) so:

$$\text{Action(XX part)} = \int \frac{m}{2} \frac{d}{dt} \left(A \frac{dA}{dt} \right) = \frac{m}{2} \frac{dA(T)}{dt} / A(T) \quad ((6)) \text{ because } A(T_f - T_f) = 0.$$

Thus, the XX part of the action is $\frac{dA(T)}{dt} / A(T)$. How does this compare to the value of $b(t)$ in $\exp(-i[b(t) XX + \dots])$? As shown in part 1, inserting this propagator into the Schrodinger equation yields:

$$\frac{db}{dt} = \frac{4bb}{2m} + k(t) \quad ((7))$$

Using the equation of motion ((6)) to eliminate the time dependent oscillator potential piece $k(t)$ yields:

$$d/dt b = 4 bb/2m -m d/dt dA/dt / A \quad ((8))$$

A solution is: $b = -m/2 dA/dt / A \quad ((9))$

This matches the classical action, and so using $\exp(-i XX b(t) + \dots)$ together with the time-dependent Schrodinger equation yields a solution for the propagator which is equivalent to the classical object $\exp(-iAction)$ (at least as far as the XX term is concerned).

Case of a $k(t)xx + mf(t)xdx/dt$ Potential

Next, consider the more general potential: $k(t)xx + mf(t)xdx/dt$

The equation of motion is:

$$m d/dt dA/dt - m A df/dt + 2k(t) A = 0 \quad ((10))$$

The Schrodinger equation approach yields the equation for the XX piece:

$$db/dt = 4/(2m) bb + k(t) + 2 bm f(t) = 2/m bb -m/2 d/dt dA/dt / A + .5 mdf/dt + 2fmb = 0 \quad ((11))$$

One may verify that: $-.5 f m -m/2 dA/dt / A \quad ((12))$ (which we later show is the XX part of the action) is a solution only if:

$$0 = df/dt - .5 ff \quad ((11b)) \text{ which is very restrictive.}$$

We now consider the classical action.

$$\{ \int dt \quad m/2 dA/dt dA/dt -k(t)AA - .5mdf/dt AA \} + [m .5f(t) AA] \text{ endpoints} \quad ((13))$$

The last term on the RHS of ((13)) results from rewriting $mf(t)x dx/dt$ in terms of a total derivative.

The classical equation of motion is:

$$md/dt dA/dt - mdf/dt A + 2k(t) A = 0 \quad ((14))$$

Multiplying ((14)) by A and evaluating ((13)) yields:

$$1/[A(T)A(T)] \int dt \quad m/2 dA/dt dA/dt + m/2 A d/dt dA/dt \text{ or}$$

$$M dA/dt/A(T) \text{ which is added to } [m .5f(t) AA] \text{ endpoints} \quad ((15)) \text{ with } A(Tf-Tf)=0$$

Thus, adding an $f(t) \times dx/dt$ term to the potential leads to the $\exp(i \text{ Action})$ and $\exp\{-i [b(t)XX + \dots]\}$ -Schrodinger equation approaches yielding different solutions unless $f(t)$ satisfies ((11b))

Case of a Time Dependent Mass

It seems there are difficulties linking the $\exp\{-i [b(t)XX + \dots]\}$ time-dependent Schrodinger approach with that of $\exp(i \text{ Action})$ for the case of a time dependent mass.

Consider the Lagrangian: $L = g(t) dA/dt - k(t)A(t)A(t)$ ((16))

The equation of motion is: $d/dt [g dA/dt] + k(t)A = 0$ ((17))

Thus: $\text{Action} = 1/[A(T)A(T)] \int dt d/dt \{ g A dA/dt \} = g A dA/dt \text{ at } T$ ((18))

The Schrodinger equation approach yields: $d/dt b = 4 g(t) b b + k(t)$ ((19))

But, $b = -dA/dt / A$ is not a solution unless $g(t) g(t) 4 = 1$ i.e. $g(t) = 1/2$ from the $1/2m$ solution.

One may still link $b(t)$ from the Schrodinger equation approach to $A(t)$, a classical Newton's law solution, as done in part I, but overall one does not seem to have $\exp(-i \text{ Action})$ in this case.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that for a constant mass, the potential $k(t)xx$ leads to a propagator which satisfies both a Schrodinger equation with propagator $= Q(t) \exp\{-i [b(t)XX \text{ etc}]$ and $Q(t)\exp(-i \text{ Action})$ where $\text{Action} = \int dt L$ with L being the Lagrangian. Thus, one has a solution of the time-dependent Schrodinger equation (i.e the propagator) which may be expressed in a completely classical manner i.e $\exp(-i \text{ Action})$ at least for XX portions.

In the case of the potential $k(t)xx + mf(t)x dx/dt$, the two approaches no longer yield the same propagator unless $f(t)$ satisfies $0 = df/dt - .5 ff$. It may be noted, that classically, the Lagrangian for this potential may be converted into one with $k_1(t)xx + d/dt[.5mf(t)xx]$. Throwing away $d/dt[.5mf(t)xx]$ yields only a $k_1(t)xx$ potential. Thus, two different Lagrangians yield the same classical equations of motion, but lead to two different time dependent Schrodinger equations with different propagators. This shows a marked difference between the classical approach and quantum mechanics.

In the case of a time dependent mass, the two approaches i.e. the Schrodinger equation solution and $\exp(-i \text{ Action})$ also do not seem to yield the same coefficient of the XX portion. One may still link $b(t)$, the coefficient of XX in the Schrodinger equation approach with the classical Newton's law solution as shown in part 1.

References

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